

**INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR FORMING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN'S
CONCEPTS ABOUT THE SUN AND PLANETS**

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Annotation: In this article, it is possible to see the existence of pre-school children and related events and situations aimed at loving nature. The need to explain the role of nature in child education and the need to use it rationally is emphasized, and innovative solutions for forming concepts of the sun and earth planets in preschool children are mentioned in detail.

Key words: Pre-school educational institution, nature, human, role, Central Asia, thinker, protection, thought, history, introduction, method, science, innovative approaches.

Introduction: With the honor of independence, great attention is being paid to the upbringing of a mentally mature, physically healthy and intellectually mature generation in our country. In such conditions, our traditions of raising children in the family are closely connected with the spirit and needs of the time and show their importance. Therefore, the issue of strengthening the family and strengthening its place in terms of spiritual and moral education is the main link of our state's policy. organic and inorganic worlds, plant and animal worlds surrounding humanity with their various forms and components. Humanity is a creature that emerged from it and separated from it. Therefore, one essence of it is natural (biological), and the other essence is social. The processes of modernization of the country also affect the economic, social, spiritual and ideological foundations of the family, which is an important institution of civil society.

Literature analysis and discussion

The importance of introducing children to nature. Love for nature is a very comprehensive and complex feeling. It forms a complex whole that includes high spiritual and academic layers. According to M. Umarova, who conducted research on the formation of a responsible attitude to the environment in preschool children, it is of great pedagogical importance to start educating this feeling from an early age. Every child grows a desire to look at the local country where he lives and the nature of Uzbekistan with love, to put his heart into it. This feeling born in childhood develops and enriches during school years. In the research work, the Methodist scientist A.V. Zaporozhets's opinion is relevant: the didactics of preschool age should be developed in such a way that children are not only aware of the external aspects of the objects around them, but also the simplest connections between them, the closest causes of the observed phenomena, let them get acquainted with some features of their changes and development, such material is not only suitable for the level, but also interesting for a preschooler.

By understanding these connections, the child learns the laws of nature. Based on the above considerations, it can be said that introducing children of preschool age to nature is to educate them in the right attitude to nature and to understand real knowledge about the environment based on emotional experience. According to observations, children's activities in the environment are mostly spontaneous and unexpected, and this is the main reason for their attitude towards nature. the calculation will be correct. Family, neighborhood, in a word, with the pedagogical influence of the surrounding people, especially the educators of the preschool educational institution, such illegal activities are corrected. That is why it is very important for children to acquire reliable information about nature even before school age. In order for children to correctly perceive natural phenomena, it is necessary to direct the process of their perception of nature.

It is impossible to successfully solve the task of educating children of preschool age in all aspects - mentally, aesthetically, morally, physically - without introducing children to nature and using it widely in the educational work of preschool educational institutions. Educational tasks of introducing children to nature. Sensory culture is an integral part of mental education. It is related to the improvement of analyzers, the strengthening of emotional experience in children, which is the basis for further generalizations, and natural science. aimed at forming initial concepts. Children's acquisition of knowledge about nature should be strongly connected with their cognitive abilities - sensory apparatus, logical thinking, attention, speech, observation, interest in learning, etc. In order to develop thinking and form a scientific worldview, it is necessary to introduce children to natural phenomena, teach them to understand the observed phenomena, and make them understand the connections and relationships between them. Causal connections and relationships between natural phenomena in the process of understanding develop thinking. The child perceives certain properties of the surrounding environment and nature: the hotness and coldness of the air with his skin, the taste of liquids with his tongue, the smell in the air with his nose, the variety in nature. perceiving the color of different objects with his eyes and sounds with his ears, i.e. these properties affect the five different senses of the child through the nerve cells located in these organs reaches the brain, and as a result, knowledge about some properties of nature appears in the brain, their appearances, images, images, landscapes are created. It is also important to educate children's interest in learning. By showing children how to observe animals and plants, focusing their attention on their appearance and behavior, the educator not only develops knowledge about nature, but also a responsible attitude towards them. It is only necessary to always take into account the age of the child and know what to focus his attention on in this matter and event. The most important thing is to ensure that children enjoy the process and results of the work they are doing. in order to form the quality of hard work, it is necessary to introduce children to the work of adults in nature, to cultivate respect for their work. nurturing the

animals and plants present in the preschool educational institution will help to educate children in an active and cautious attitude towards nature.

Conclusion: An educator is required to be able to organize a corner of living nature, to create conditions for plants and animals close to their living in nature. In addition, he should be able to master the agrotechnical methods of watering plants and feeding animals on the grounds of the preschool educational institution and in the nature corner. The teacher's example has a decisive effect on the development of labor skills in children. In the process of forming children's knowledge about nature, it is very important for the educator to be able to see the beauty of nature and to have the desire to create beauty in nature. In addition to acquiring the necessary knowledge and skills, it is also necessary to master the use of forms, methods and tools of introduction to nature.

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